
Blueberry occurring Platygastriidae (Hymenoptera: Platygastroidea) in the Eastern USA with special emphasis on parasitoids of the blueberry gall midge complex, *Dasineura oxycoccana* and *Prodiplosis vacinii* (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae)

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Abstract

Blueberries have been an important food source in North America since before European colonization and remain economically and culturally significant. The Blueberry Gall Midge Complex (BGMC), consisting of *Dasineura oxycoccana* and *Prodiplosis vacinii*, poses a serious threat to blueberry crops, causing up to 80–90% bud loss and long-term plant damage. Current control methods are based on insecticides, which face challenges due to the biology of the midge and the increasing demand for organic produce. The nature of BGMC infestation, paired with prolonged periods of abundance, requires an integrated pest management approach. Parasitoid wasps, particularly of the subfamily Platygastriinae, show promise as biocontrol agents, but limited identification tools hinder effective IPM. This study offers information on the platygastriid fauna of blueberry plantations in the Eastern United States and an identification key to distinguish those parasitizing the blueberry gall midge from those likely unrelated, thereby assisting IPM professionals in monitoring effective natural enemies through mass collection techniques.

Keywords

Blueberry Gall Midge Complex, Platygastriinae, Integrated Pest Management, parasitoid wasps, biocontrol, Cecidomyiinae, natural enemies, DNA barcoding, pest management strategies, sustainable agriculture.

Introduction

Wild high and low bush blueberry fruits have been a naturally occurring food source in the United States since before European colonization. The fruits were a dietary staple for the indigenous peoples of North America, introduced to European colonists, and likely incorporated into the tablescape of the first Thanksgiving (Pankau, 2021). Today, numerous varieties of blueberries grown in the United States contribute to local economies and the cultural identities of agricultural communities. In 2019, the value of the US blueberry crop (primarily highbush varieties) was estimated at \$909 million.

A handful of insect pests threaten domestic blueberry crops, and understanding their biology and phenology—as well as that of their natural enemies—is critical for developing sustainable

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integrated pest management strategies (Burrack et al., 2020). One area for improvement is the knowledge base surrounding the Blueberry Gall Midge Complex (BGMC, Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) and their associated natural enemies (Sampson et al., 2013). The BGMC comprises two gall midge species, *Dasineura oxycoccana* and *Prodiplosis vaccinii* that are emerging pests in northern highbush, southern highbush, rabbiteye, lowbush, and half-high blueberries (Collins and Drummond, 2019). BGMC can be extremely injurious, causing 20–80% crop loss on highbush blueberries in the southern United States and in Michigan (Burrack et al., 2020; Sampson et al., 2002; Lyrene and Payne, 1992; Hahn and Isaacs, 2012). Larvae of BGMC damages plant tissue and results in flower bud loss (30–50% in Maine, 80–90% in Florida) and substantial injury to vegetative shoots in both Maine and Michigan (Collins and Drummond, 2019; Sampson et al., 2002; Hahn and Isaacs, 2012). As BGMC distorts leaves and destroys vegetative tissues, it reduces the plant’s capacity to support a heavy berry crop in future seasons (Steck et al., 2000; Bosio et al., 1998).

Chemical insecticides are the present foundation for managing BGMC, despite significant obstacles and consequences (Burrack et al., 2020). Due to the concealed nature of larvae within plant tissues and the short lifespan of adult midges, insecticides are difficult to apply effectively. Even accurately timed applications can seriously threaten pollinator and natural enemy populations (Liburd and Phillips, 2019). Insecticide application is also increasingly unpopular among consumers who value organic certification for a food item widely known for its health benefits.

Parasitoid wasps in the families Platygasteridae, Ceraphronidae, and Eulophidae, and predatory hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) have been reported as potential biocontrol agents of the BGMC (Barnes, 1948; Mahr and Kachadoorian, 1990; Sampson et al., 2002, 2006; Fitzpatrick et al., 2018). In rearing experiments, one eulophid species (*Aprostocetus*) and several platygasterid species (in the genera *Synopeas*, *Inostemma*, and *Platygaster*) were found most effective in parasitizing BGMC in Mississippi and Florida, showing a 30–40% parasitization rate (Sampson et al., 2006; Peach et al., 2012; Roubos, 2009).

Platygasterinae (Hymenoptera: Platygasteridae), a group of cecidomyiid parasitoids, comprised 67% of the parasitoids collected from blueberry fields using yellow sticky traps (Sampson et al., 2013). Platygasterines have been effective biocontrol agents against *Dasineura* and *Orseolia* species (Ogah and Nwilene, 2014; Hidaka et al., 1974), and are also promising for managing invasive pests in North America, including Swede midge, apple leaf midge, wheat midge, and potentially soybean midge (Cossentine et al., 2020; He and Wang, 2015; Echegaray et al., 2016; Chavalle et al., 2018; Dufton et al., 2021; Kee, 2019; Harris, 2019).

Integrated pest management in blueberries must rely on predicting the peak emergence of BGMC and its natural enemies due to the narrow window for applying non-systemic pesticides (Roubos, 2009; Hahn and Isaacs, 2012). Yellow sticky traps and bowls are ineffective for predicting BGMC peaks (Roubos and Liburd, 2010; Collins and Drummond, 2019), and emergence traps are useful only early in the season, leaving leaf bud dissection as the most reliable method for estimating BGMC phenology (Collins and Drummond, 2019; Sarzynski and Liburd, 2003). While all methods are useful for monitoring BGMC parasitoids, accurate identification of BGMC parasitoids is essential, as emergence traps may also collect unrelated species.

The lack of identification tools for platygasterid parasitoids in blueberry hinders accurate phenology estimation and the development of effective IPM strategies. To address this, we identify platygasterid taxa in blueberry crops in New England and the southeastern U.S., use abundance surveys and rearing experiments to link taxa to the blueberry gall midge complex, and provide diagnostic tools for identifying these parasitoids, focusing on morphological traits guiding blueberry pest managers in the identification of effective blueberry parasitoids.

Materials and Methods

Specimens (<https://github.com/teleaslamellatus/Blueberry-gallmidge-parasitoids>) were collected using malaise traps and yellow pan traps and were extracted from the terminal vegetation of blueberry plants which indicated tissue damage consistent with BGMC. The initiation of field collection

activities in New England was timed using estimated *Dasineura oxycoccana* adult emergence by thermal constants in degree days. These values were approximated to a small range of K=131.0-134.2, based on a lower temperature threshold of 8.9 ° C (Roubos, 2009). Specimens for the present study are deposited in the UNH Entomological Collection (Durham, NH, USA).

For the duration of the active season, Townes-style malaise traps (BugDorm) were erected at collection sites and serviced every two weeks. In addition, we performed several 24-hour yellow pan trapping events at each site using 150 x 12oz plastic yellow bowls (Coco Loco Party Center) with tap water and 2 drops of biodegradable non-foaming dish soap (Seventh Generation). Following the sorting of mass-collected samples, platygastriid specimens were identified to the generic level, cataloged using TaxonWorks, and either stored in ethanol for DNA extraction or mounted for curation.

Specimens were mounted following, or immediately upon exclusion from DNA extraction. Morphological characters were scored by observing specimens with a Huvitz stereomicroscope equipped with an Olympus DF PL 2× objective. Brightfield images of dried specimens were taken with an Olympus CX41 compound microscope equipped with a Canon EOS 6D digital camera. Image stacking was performed with Zerene Stacker (Version 1.04 Build T201404082055; Zerene Systems LLC, Richland, WA). Extended focus images were annotated and modified with Adobe Photoshop 2023 (Adobe Systems, San Jose, CA) using the Adjust/Levels/Auto and Image/Adjustments/Exposure (Gamma correction) tools.

Results and discussion

14 genera of Platygastriidae were detected across seven blueberry field collecting sites, including *Aceroteta* Kozlov & Masner, 1977; *Allotropa* Förster, 1856; *Amblyaspis* Förster, 1856; *Amitus* Haldeman, 1850; *Eritrissomerus* Ashmead, 1893; *Euxestonotus* Fouts, 1925; *Fidiobia* Ashmead, 1894; *Inostemma* Haliday, 1833; *Iphitrachelus* Walker, 1835; *Isostasius* Förster, 1856; *Leptacis* Förster, 1856; *Metanopedias* Brues, 1910; *Platygaster* Latreille, 1809; *Synopeas* Förster 1856; and *Trichacis* Förster, 1856. Majority of the 615 platygastriid specimens collected in the present study belong to *Platygaster* (171) and *Synopeas* (242). The third most commonly collected platygastriid genus is *Amblyaspis* (81).

Site	PSREU	Island Grove	PPSP	BHF	Woodman	BBF	New Durham	TOTAL
<i>Allotropa</i>	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
<i>Amblyaspis</i>	0	0	0	18	63	0	0	81
<i>Amitus</i>	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
<i>Eritrissomerus</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Euxestonotus</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Fidiobia</i>	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Inostemma</i>	0	2	0	1	2	0	0	5
<i>Iphitrachelus</i>	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
<i>Isostasius</i>	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
<i>Leptacis</i>	4	0	1	3	32	1	0	24
<i>Piestopleura</i>	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Platygaster</i>	23	2	0	7	119	15	2	171
<i>Synopeas</i>	19	3	4	63	119	13	6	242
<i>Trichacis</i>	1	0	0	2	3	1	0	7
<i>Undetermined</i>	1	0	3	0	2	0	0	38
TOTAL	53	7	3	79	222	29	8	615

Table 1. Species distribution across various sites in FL, ME, and NH.

Synopeas was the most abundant genus of all platygastriids in blueberry. The most abundant *Synopeas* that we identified across each of our study sites were *Synopeas pennsylvanicum* Fouts and *Synopeas* nr. *varipes* n. sp. The greatest proportion of our *S. pennsylvanicum* were collected

at Blueberry Hill Farm in Maine, and the greatest proportion of *S.* near *varipes* n. sp. was from Woodman Farm in New Hampshire. The greatest share of our *S.* nr. *varipes* were collected at Woodman Farm in New Hampshire where *Prodiplosis* spp. were identified in northern highbush blueberry, *Vaccinium corymbosum*. The second most abundant genus detected was *Platygaster*, which merits a future, deep investigation using the same methods as in the present study. In addition to *Synopeas* and *Platygaster*, thirteen other platygastriidae genera were identified in significantly lower numbers. *Inostemma*, which was reared in 2006 in Mississippi (Sampson et al., 2006)), proved to be relatively rare in our mass collected samples, composing 5 out of 615 total specimens.

Our reared specimen was consistent with the Sampson et al. (2006) experiments where *S. pennsylvanicum* was reared from southern highbush blueberry, *Vaccinium corymbosum* × *Vaccinium darrowii*, in Mississippi, where both *Dasineura oxycoccana* and *Prodiplosis vaccinii* were suspected. This was also the most abundant species detected from our synopean specimens across all sites. The parasitoidization by *Synopeas pennsylvanicum* in two geographically distant regions and blueberry host plant species strengthens its candidacy as a biological control agent for the blueberry gall midge complex.

Identification key to BGMC parasitoid *Synopeas* species

1. Wing venation distinct (Fig 2A) **Sceliotrachelinae** part
Wing venation absent or indistinct (reduced) (Figs 2B, C) **2**
2. Foamy structures (semitransparent outgrowth with irregular appearance) present (Fig. 3A), shorter and usually flattened species **Sceliotrachelinae part** (*Amitus*, *Fidiobia*)
Foamy structure absent, usually elongate species (Figs 3B)..... **3**
3. Left and right lateral propodeal carina are separated medially, distance between carinae at least half the length of each carina (Figs 4A, D) **Platygastrinae** ex Synopeadini
Left and right lateral propodeal carina are continuous medially (Figs 4C, F) or distance between carinae less than half the length of each carina (Figs 4B, E, Synopeadini) **4**
4. Ventral pronotal pit absent or reduced (Fig. 5A, C); T1-T2 suture present, anterior portion of metasoma rarely setose (Figs 5A, B) **Leptacis** Förster 1856
ventral pronotal pit distinct (Figs 5B, 6C); T1-T2 suture absent (syntergum and synsternum present), anterior portion of metasoma densely setose (Figs 6B, C)(*Synopeas*) **5**
5. Scutoscutellar sulcus deep (deep divide between the mesoscutum and mesoscutellum present) (Figs 6A, B) *Synopeas rhanis*-group sensu Melotto et al. (2023)
Scutoscutellar sulcus shallow (deep divide between the mesoscutum and mesoscutellum absent) (pof: Figs 7C, 8A, B)..... **6**
6. Scutes on head with concave surface, scutes separated from each other by carinae (Figs 7B, D, E); Median mesoscutal projection finger-like (elongate with rounded tip), sculptured and without ventral lamella-like structure (pof: Figs 7C, 8A, B, *Synopeas varipes*-group)..... **7**
Scutes on frons with convex or flat surfaces, separated from each other by sulci (Fig. 7A, 9B-G); Median mesoscutal projection not finger-like (if elongate tip not rounded), smooth, with or without ventral lamella-like structure (Figs 5B, 9A)..... **9**
7. a. Ventral margin of synsternite more convex, synsternite much higher than syntergite in lateral view (Fig. 7C)..... ***Synopeas (Sactogaster)*** sp.
aa. Ventral margin of synsternite less convex, synsternite as high as syntergite in lateral view (Figs 8A, B)..... **8**

8. Hyperoccipital carina present (Figs 8A, D); OOL more than two times as long as median ocellus diameter (Figs 8D); Sculpture of pronotum extends posteriorly to pronoto-mesopectal suture and exceeds ventrally midlevel of pronotum (Fig. 8A); Central keel present on dorsal region of frons (Fig. 7E) *Synopeas nr. varipes* n. sp. 135-138
- Hyperoccipital carina absent (Figs 8B, C); OOL more than two times as long as median ocellus diameter (Fig. 8C); Sculpture of pronotum not extends posteriorly to pronoto-mesopectal suture and and not exceeds ventrally midlevel of pronotum (Fig. 8B); Central keel absent just from dorsal region of frons (Fig. 7D) *Synopeas varipes* Harrington 1899 139-142
8. Dorsal margin of Mesoscutellar spine straight; ventral lamella like structure on mesoscutellar spine present (Figs 5B, 9A); Frons transversely striated and submedian ocellar carinae present (Figs 9B-G)..... *Synopeas pennsylvanicum* Fouts 1924 143-145
- Dorsal margin of mesoscutellar spine not straight (e.g. Figs 8A, B); Frons not transversely striated and submedian ocellar carinae absent (e.g. Figs 7A, D, E)..... *Synopeas* sp. 146-148

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Figure 1. The blueberry gall midge complex (BGMC) and its parasitoids. A, B. Confocal Laser Scanning micrograph showing the external and internal morphology of a platygastriid wasp (*Amitus* sp.). C, D. Brightfield images of platygastriids reared from larvae of BGMC in Maine June 2021 (*Synopeas* sp.). Intact specimen with the host puparium (C) and specimen bleached with H₂O₂ to increase the contrast of external characters (D). E. BGMC larvae collected from a single gall in Maine, June 2021. Larvae might represent specimens of different developmental stadia or of different species.

Figure 2. Fore wings of Platygastriidae. A. *Inostemma* sp., B. *Amitus* sp., C. *Synopeas* nr. *varipes*

Figure 3. Head and mesosoma of Platygastridae. A. *Amitus* sp. showing "foamy structures on the posterior region of the metapectal-propodeal complex. B. *Platygaster* sp.

Figure 4. Posterior mesosoma of Platygastriinae showing the composition of lateral propodeal carinae. A, D. *Platygaster* sp., B, E. *Leptacis* sp., C, F. *Synopeas* sp.

Figure 5. Synopeadini showing the presence /absence of ventral pronotal pit. A, C. Lateral view of *Leptacis* sp., B. *Synopeas pennsylvanicum*.

Figure 6. Synopeadini. A. Metasoma of *Leptacis* sp., B. Metasoma of *Synopeas* nr. *varipes*, C. *Synopeas rhanis*-group

Figure 7. Synopeadini. A. Head of *Leptacis* sp. B. Head of *Synopeas* nr. *varipes*, C. *Synopeas* (*Sactogaster*) sp. D. *Synopeas varipes*, E. *Synopeas* nr. *varipes*)

Figure 8. Lateral habitus and dorsal head of *Synopeas varipes*-group. A, C. *S. varipes*, B. *S. nr. varipes*.

Figure 9. *Synopeas pennsylvanicum*. A. Lateral habitus, B–G. Anterior head showing the variability of frontal striation.